

A Service Learning experience with engineering students

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Abstract

Service learning is an educational approach that combines learning processes and community service in a single well-articulated project, in which all participants work on the real needs of the environment with the aim of improving it. The service learning experience presented in this paper aimed to provide students with the opportunity to develop technical and transversal skills in a real context of practice, taking also in consideration the social needs of the community and environment where the students are inserted. The participants in the study included seven teams of students, with 3 to 5 group members each, enrolled in the curricular unit called “Lean Enterprise”, which took place from October to December 2019 at the University of Minho. Although following a Service Learning approach only two student teams were carrying out their project on social organizations (group A of students). The other 5 teams were carrying out their projects in university services and directories as well on campus research and development institutions (group B). Based on the Service Learning approach, students applied knowledge acquired in the course to help the host institutions to make their work more efficient and effective. At the end of the project, students’ feedback about their project and service learning experience was collected through an online survey, following the work of Folgueiras et al. (2018). Findings from students’ perceptions show, in general, that they had a positive view of the effects of their participation. Students from group A gave more relevance to social awareness and personal development while students from group B gave more relevance to technical and professional competences developed in the project.

Keywords: Higher Education; Service Learning; Lean Enterprise

1 Introduction

The most successful way of organizing and managing operations started to be established in the Toyota Motor Company in the 1950s under the designation of Toyota Production System (TPS). It became a major milestone in the history of the production organization and management. That way of organizing and managing work has been formalized in sets of principles and concepts in several forms. Probably the most important currents of thoughts representing it are: Lean Thinking (Womack & Jones, 1997), Shingo Model (Plenert, 2017) and Toyota Way (Liker, 2005). The principles that shape each one of the models can be divided in two main groups, the visible side and the invisible side as expressed by Mike Rother (Rother, 2010). The visible side includes principles such as value and pull production flow, as well the visible side of continuous improvement. The invisible side is more related to the human side, culture and behaviour, including principles such as: “Respect Every Individual”, “Lead with Humility”, “Embrace Scientific Thinking”, “Think Systematically”, and “Create Constancy of Purpose” from Shingo Model. Examples from the Toyota Way are (Liker, 2005): “Having a long-term philosophy that drives a long-term approach to building a learning organization”, “Grow leaders who thoroughly understand the work, live the philosophy, and teach it to others”, “Develop exceptional people and teams who follow your company’s philosophy”, “Respect your extended network of partners and suppliers by challenging them and helping them improve”, “Make decisions slowly by consensus, thoroughly considering all options; implement decisions rapidly (Nemawashi), and “Become a learning organization through relentless reflection (hansei) and continuous improvement (Kaizen)”.

The roots of Service based Learning (SbL) or also called Service Learning go back to the beginning of the 20th century when Arthur Dunn incorporated service project in the community as part of his social studies curriculum (Nieboer, 2000). The term “Service Learning” was introduced in the 1970s (Southern Regional Education Board, 1970) stating among other things that universities should encourage student to do community service, assist in assuring learning as part of this service as well as stating that students, college

faculty and staff, cooperate in the administration of programs in which students both serve and learn. Service learning is an educational approach that combines learning processes and community service in a single well-articulated project in which all participants are working on real needs of the environment with the aim of improving it (Casares, 2013). Service learning programs are very similar to Project-based Learning on which our research group has long experience (PBL) (Lima et al., 2017). The main difference is that the real context in SL are social organizations instead of companies. Learning while developing projects in real context is recognized to be more effective than traditional classroom learning but SL is also believed to hold the potential to broaden and significantly enhance the learning climate for students (Levesque-Bristol, Knapp, & Fisher, 2011). The general learning goals of Service-Learning can be organized in three categories (Felten & Clayton, 2011): civic learning; academic learning and personal growth. Service Learning programs can be found in many universities in Europe (EOSLHE, 2020), in many universities in USA where we stand out Purdue University (EPICS program) (Purdue University, 2020), as well as in general across the world.

Service-learning projects imply challenges in the development of community actions that have a high educational component. Knowing the needs and realities of other groups and encouraging people to contribute with their input allows stereotypes to be changed and contributes to rebuilding social links. In service-learning projects, people in situations of exclusion are no longer beneficiaries of solidarity-based actions to become agents of change, and service actions are opportunities to incorporate their voices, input and contributions in the building of inclusive citizenship.

The implementation of lean principles and concepts in social organizations is not completely new. One example comes from Jefferson County (Murman & Bakst, 2017) and another one refer non-profit organizations discovering lean advantages (Murray & Ma, 2015). Attending to Lean Thinking principles, it is in this kind of organizations and services that lean makes even more sense, due to the scarce resources they have (Shafiq & Soratana, 2020). Some local communities have been benefiting of such services, namely, the local communities where the Lean Sigma Academy of the UTRGV-Texas Manufacturing Assistance Centre is integrated (UTRGV, 2020). One of the few examples about learning Lean Six Sigma with Service-Learning is provided by Braun (Braun, 2013). Higher education institutions have formal social responsibility expressed in many different ways. In Portugal one of these ways is expressed in the so called "Green book on Social responsibility of HEI" (*Livro Verde sobre Responsabilidade Social e Instituições de Ensino Superior*, 2018). By strengthening the community - university partnerships, universities can contribute to bring solutions to the major challenges of the 21st century, such as increasing environmental and socio-economic crises, inequalities of income and wealth and political instabilities (von Hauff & Nguyen, 2014). These challenges are also at the heart of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by the all United Nations Member States in 2015 (Johnston, 2016). The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are an urgent call for action by all countries - developed and developing - in a global partnership. By integrating lean principles and practices into social organizations, through active engagement of engineering students in community projects, universities can lead by example. Furthermore, through curriculum innovation and active learning approaches, future decision makers can learn the competences needed to solve ecological, social, and economic problems in societies, along with the development of human competences and civic awareness (Cumbo & Vadeboncoeur, 1998; Folgueiras, Aramburuzabala, Opazo, Mugarra, & Ruiz, 2018). Service Learning plays a crucial role to support HEI to achieve these goals (*Livro Verde sobre Responsabilidade Social e Instituições de Ensino Superior*, 2018).

This study aims to describe a service learning experience carried out with fifth year students of an engineering programme at the University of Minho, Portugal. The learning approach followed the principles of SL, combined with PBL. Students worked in teams and applied knowledge acquired in the curricular unit of "Lean Enterprise" to help social and non-social organizations make their work more efficient and capable. As not all groups had the opportunity to develop their project in a social organization, this paper aims to analyse if there are any differences in terms of the participation, type of service, the competences developed and the general satisfaction, between students who developed their project in a social organization and students who did not. What conclusions can be drawn from this comparison? Which of these dimensions presented results that were most surprising? What are the implications for practice?

In the next sections, we will provide a description of the context of the study, followed by the methodology and results, which are organized and discussed according to the impact of the project on the social / non-social organizations and students' perceptions about the SL experience, based on the application of a survey (Folgueiras et al., 2018).

2 Context of the study

This study took place at the end of 2019 at the University of Minho in 2019 with students from the 5th year of the Integrated Masters in Engineering and Industrial Management. These students were enrolled in the curricular unit "Lean Enterprise" which includes every year a project in a real context to develop skills in the areas of Lean thinking applied in a non-industrial context. It is also the aim of the project that students develop important transversal skills for their future as professionals. Projects usually follow a Project Based Learning fashion and are carried out in internal services of the university such as administrative services, technical services, master's degrees directories, and departmental directories. In 2019 the responsible for the curricular unit decided to also include some projects outside the university walls in social organizations. Two social organizations agreed to join the project and for that reason the framework of this type of learning model became a kind of a mix of Project Based Learning (PBL) and Service Learning (SL). In fact the adopted system followed more the SL guidelines than the PBL. The 31 students organized themselves in 7 teams and each team selected the service or social organization of their preference to carry out the project.

Table 1 – Host institutions and project general objectives.

Host Institution	Team size	Project objectives
RB - Refood in Braga	5	Analyse and Improve processes
RG - Refood in Guimaraes	5	Analyse and Improve processes
TM - TecMinho	5	Introduce Lean Office Tools
PIEP – Innovation in polymers Institute	5	Introduce Continuous Improvement
DEP – Polymer department directory	3	Analyse and Improve processes
PSD – Technical Office at PSD	3	Implement Lean Green practices
DSI – Technical Office at ISD	5	Apply Lean practices

The list of host institutions and project objectives is shown in Table . Refood in Braga and Refood in Guimaraes are social organizations with the purpose of collecting free food supplied by local restaurants and delivering it to people in need in the same region. TecMinho is a private non-profit association founded in 1990, having as sponsors the University of Minho and the Association of Municipalities of Vale do Ave. PIEP (innovation in polymers) is also a non-profit organization created in 2001, at the initiative of the plastics and moulds sector, in close collaboration with the University of Minho, through the Department of Polymer Engineering and IAPMEI. The other three host institutions are services in the same building of our department (PSD - Production and Systems Department) being one of them the Directory of the Polymer Department, the other one the Technical office in our department, and the technical office of the Information and Systems Department (ISD).

Each host institution has assigned the responsibility of accompanying students during the project to someone from the institution with the responsibility of guiding the student team in the project. Students would have to spend some time every week in the host institution performing their project tasks and also meet weekly with project supervisor to show the project progress and obtain feedback. The teams had to present their work 3 times during the project to obtain feedback and had to perform a final presentation at the end of the semester with highest wait in terms of assessment. Each team also had to assess the other teams in their final public presentation and that assessment was only used by the curricular unit coordinator to help the fine tune the final grades. The project was assessed by the quality of team's presentations in terms of communication effectiveness, the quality of the technical solutions proposed and implemented, the quality of the results.

According to Aramburuzabala, Cerrillo, & Tello (2015), the project results should be celebrated and disseminated with all the participants involved in the SL project. For this final celebration, students at University of Minho organized a final event, open to the academia and the local community. All the host institutions were invited, and the student teams performed brief public presentation, with the main results of their projects and the improvement suggestions implemented in each context. These presentations were not subject to any formal assessment of students. The people representing host institutions were asked to give specific feedback from the project in their institutions as well as general feedback for the initiative. A discussion was then promoted in terms of the initiative impact on students in terms of personal growth and social awareness as well as the projects role in the community. Finally everyone was invited to get together in a more informal way in a reserved area of the building cafeteria to share some snacks and drinks and socialize. Figure shows on the left side the flyer created by the students to formalize the event and invite institutions and on the right side one picture of the final informal socialization.

Figure 1 - Flyer of the Final Event (left) and celebration of SL results (right)

3 Methodology

At the end of the project, students' feedback about their project and service learning experience was collected through an online survey, following the work of a group of experts of service-learning in Spanish Higher Education (Folgueiras et al., 2018). These authors developed an instrument to analyse the impact of service learning on four main concepts or elements: Participation, Service, Competences and General Satisfaction. Figure 2 presents the dimensions included in the questionnaire, which included different type of questions (scale, closed, multiples responses, exclusive and non-exclusive responses). The questionnaire was kindly shared and authorised, by the original authors, to be applied at the context of the University of Minho.

To enrich the data collection, 4 open-ended questions were added to the online questionnaire aimed at identifying the most positive (strengths) and less positive (weakness) aspects and suggestions for improvements. So, for the analysis, both quantitative and qualitative data will be considered.

The participants in the project included 31 students, 20 male and 11 female. Students' ages ranged from 21 to 25 years old. The questionnaire was sent to all students, by email, after the conclusion of the project. The sample of this study includes 21 participants, who voluntarily answered the questionnaire.

Concepts/elements	Dimensions	Indicators	Items/scale measures
Participation	Levels of participation	Participation throughout the project Participation at some points Participation in needs analysis Participation in assessment New projects Decision to carry out one or other activity	10 and 11: closed, multiple responses, non-exclusive
	Factors conditioning participation	Personal motivation; liking for project type, putting course contents in practice etc. Organizational aspects: distance, timetable etc.	9, 12: scale
Service	Description of service	Field: health promotion, rights promotion etc. Type of service: direct/ indirect Beneficiaries: individuals/ groups/institutions	1, 2 and 3: closed, multiple responses, exclusive
	Opinion of project usefulness	Usefulness of the service for working on course contents, understanding needs etc.	4, 5, 6 and 7: scale
Competences	General and transversal	Instrumental: finding and managing information etc. Interpersonal: teamwork etc. Systemic: organizing and planning etc.	8: scale
Transversal	General satisfaction	Participation: organizational engagement etc. Service: service activities carried out etc. Competences: curriculum contents etc. Others: project impacts etc.	14 and 16: closed, multiple responses, non-exclusive 15: scale

Figure 2 - Relationships between concepts/dimensions/indicators/items and scale measurement of the SL Questionnaire (Folgueiras et al., 2018, p. 6)

4 Results

The results section is organized in three parts. The first part describes the impact of students' projects on the host institutions, showing the improvements developed by students in each host institution. The second part discusses students' feedback about the experience, based on the results from the application of the questionnaire developed by Folgueiras et al. (2018). The third part presents a comparison of students' perceptions, when divided into two groups, according to the context where their project took place: a social organization (group A) or another type of organization (group B). An attempt to identify differences in students' perceptions is explored in this last subsection.

4.1 Improvements in the host institutions

The type of improvements that were proposed and implemented in each host institution by each student team is shown in Table 2. The 5S technique and One-Point-Lessons/Standards were the most common implementation being applied in 5 of the 7 host institutions. The implementation of 5S was quite expected because it is probably the most common lean tool being implemented when organizations start a lean journey. One-Point-Lessons and Standards are also in line with 5S helping creating more discipline and organization in production or office areas. The second most proposed and implemented lean practice was material flow mechanisms. The material flow mechanisms were designed to keep the flow of materials, such as food or office material, avoiding stagnation or shortage. The teams implemented mechanisms such as Kanban and two bin systems to control the flow and stock of materials.

Table 2 – List of lean practices that were proposed and implemented.

Lean Practice	Host Institution						
	RB	RG	TM	PIEP	DEP	PSD	DSI
5S technique	I	I	I		I		I
One-Point-Lessons/Standardization	I		I		I	I	I
Flow mechanisms (Kanban/Two bin System)	I	P			I	I	
5S audits		P	P		P		
Improve information flow		I			P		P
Visual Management	I	I		I			
Improve Layout	I	P					
Poka-Yoke			I			I	
KPI development and monitoring				I			
Team boards				I			
Team meetings				I			
Reutilization and recycling mechanisms						I	
Energy savings						I	
<i>"I" – Implemented;</i> <i>"P" – Proposed and not implemented until the end of the project</i>							

Other implementations shared by tree teams were the 5S audits system, solutions to improve information flow and visual management solutions. Regarding the 5S audits systems the teams designed a check list appropriated to the context as well as the definition of the audit people and its periodicity. Visual management solutions were implemented by three teams in order to simplify management and monitor the work to be performed. The other lean practices were implemented only by two or one team.

4.2 Students' feedback about the Experience

In general, students' feedback about the project experience was considered positive. An overall analysis of the results from the questionnaire reveal a positive opinion of students in regard to the four main categories of questions included in the questionnaire: general satisfaction, type of service provided, level of participation and competences acquired by taking part in the project (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Overall results of the survey, according to the four main categories of the questionnaire

As shown in Figure 3, students' general satisfaction with their projects shows the highest average (4.3), when compared with the other three categories, which also reveal positive results. Despite the host institution where the projects were carried out, all students showed a positive opinion about their project experience. Some of the qualitative data collected from the students, referring to what they liked most about the project, elucidate the aspects most valued by students. The following quotes from students confirm this: *to be able to apply what we learn in theory; having a positive impact on an organization; the power to have had a beneficial impact on the organization in which the project took place; real case in an organization; the people involved in the project; to see how it was actually possible to implement most of the suggestions in a timely manner and see the results; interaction with the organizations.*

The development of competences is also one of the most evident results of the impact of PBL and SL on student learning and personal development. Besides the technical competences that students are strongly encouraged to develop through the improvements implemented in the host institutions, as previously explored in section 4.1. of this result analysis, students clearly recognized a set of transversal competences that were effectively developed through the project. The competences that were most positively evaluated, as shown in Figure 4, were teamwork (4.63), adapting to new situations (4.4), problem-solving (4.4), ethical commitment (4.38) and communicating orally and in writing (4.38). These competences are both common to PBL and SL approaches, which is not a surprising result, as both approaches share the principle of “learning by doing” and teamwork is an important asset for the successful development of the project. The items from the questionnaire, regarding competences development, that were rated less positively were foreign language learning (2.0), knowledge of ICTs (3.13) and expressing feeling (3.13). This fact may be due to the nature of the projects developed and the specific objectives which they entailed. It is also important to refer that most of these students who participated in the project have already some experience in PBL, as this is one of the most favoured methodologies of the Integrated Masters in Engineering and Industrial Management (Lima et al., 2017). To conclude, the majority of the items were rated with an average above 3.5, which reveals a positive impact of the project on the development of students’ competences.

Figure 4 – Results of the questionnaire for the category “Development of Competences”

When questioned about the usefulness of the service, students mostly referred to the benefits in terms of the opportunity to put professional skills into practice (4.56), to be more consistent in their actions (4.44), to relate theory and practice (4.38), to know the professional field of their degree (4.31) and learning values (4.31). When asked about what they learned from the project, through an open-ended question, students’ answers included several dimensions related to opportunity to contact with the organization where their project took place. Some examples that confirm this are the following quotes from students: *[I learned] to understand the needs of information of companies and organizations. The attitude and initiative that you need to have in order to obtain the essential information for the completion of the project. Listening and working in groups (it is a continuous learning process); [I learned] Lean Office tools; [I learned] to put in practice; [I learned] to identify problems, discuss possible solutions, reach an agreement, propose solutions and implement solutions, evaluating the results; [I learned] the relationship between tools and the environment.*

4.3 Comparing Students' perceptions

Since some students carried out their projects in social organizations, an attempt was made to identify differences in their perceptions. For this study, students were divided into two groups, group A and group B. Students in group A carried out their projects in social organizations, students in group B carried out their projects in other organizations. From the answers collected from the questionnaire there was a clear difference between the average assessments given by the two groups. Figure 5 shows the questions that group A assessed in a clearer positive way.

Figure 5 – Questions with more positive feedback given from group A than group B.

Students from group A (project in social organizations) recognized that their project allowed them to improve society more (22% more) than students from group B. The same perception was given to the development of the ability of expressing their feelings (also 22% more to group A). With more than 18% difference in assessment was the responses given by students from group A as contributing to improve societies being the reason why they chose the project. The competence to recognize diversity and multiculturalism was also identified as being developed more positively by group A by around 10%.

Figure 6 - Questions with more positive feedback given from group B than group A.

At the other extreme we have questions whose answers from group B were in average clearly more positive (Figure 6). Students from group B perceived in a more positive way that the project provided the development of competences in the technical side. The clearest examples are shown in Figure 6 and are the connection between theory and practice, usefulness of the curriculum content, knowing their professional scope, knowing and understanding technical ideas and concepts, and to put course content into practice.

5 Conclusions

A service learning approach was experienced in a course where traditionally a PBL approach was used. In order to identify the differences when social organizations act as host institution, the students were divided in two groups. Students from group A were assigned to a project carried out in a social organization while students from group B were assigned to a project carried out in other non-profit organizations. In both cases, students developed specific technical and professional skills as well as transversal skills. A survey was applied to collect

students' perceptions. Regarding the technical and professional aspects, students highlighted that they "put professional skills into practice" (4.56 out of 5), "relate theory and practice" (4.38), and "to know the professional field of their degree" (4.31). Regarding the transversal skills students in general highlighted teamwork (with 4.63 out of 5), adapting to new situations (4.4), and problem-solving (4.4). A second part of this study was to identify possible differences between the perceptions of students from group A and students from group B. Students from group A recognized that that project allowed them to improve society much more than students from group B. Moreover, students from group A recognized much more the developed ability of expressing their feelings, as well as the competence to recognize diversity and multiculturalism. Students from group B, in general, gave more importance to the professional learnings. The overall learnings from this experience is that the advantages of Service Learning approach in improving the developing in students aspects such as social awareness and personal development is more than welcome. This is even more relevant in a course like the one referred in this study where "respect every individual" and "lead with humility" are their key principles (Plenert, 2017; Liker, 2005).

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